

Clinico-Epidemiological Profile of Stroke Patients Admitted in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Gujarat

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 26-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Aim: Strokes tend to occur more frequently in older individuals and those who have certain risk factors. These risk factors include hypertension, type 2 diabetes, previous strokes, being male, being post-menopausal as a female, dyslipidemia, and hyper-homocystenemia. This study evaluated the clinical profile of patients who presented with Stroke etiology.

Material and Methods: A total of 175 patients who were admitted to the medical ward were included in this study. Thoroughly collected medical history from all patients and conducted comprehensive examinations of all systems, with special attention to the neurological system. The patient's profile prompted the necessary investigations.

Results: There were 115 males and 60 females. The average age for infarction in the study population is 56.12 years. The most common age group was 31-40 years, with 88.57% (n=155) of the patients being older than 40 years old. Out of the 175 patients, a majority of 71.42% did not have any comorbidities. On the other hand, 28.57% of patients had known co-morbidities like diabetes mellitus, coronary heart disease, and other conditions. Type 2 diabetes had the highest prevalence among co-morbidities, affecting 19.42% of individuals, while high blood pressure followed closely behind at 5.71%.

Conclusion: Thrombotic stroke, which includes ischemic stroke and venous sinus thrombosis, is more common than hemorrhagic stroke. Stroke commonly co-occurs with type 2 diabetes mellitus and coronary heart disease (CHD), increasing the risk of developing infarcts. Patients with risk factors such as hypertension, male gender, post-menopausal female, addiction, dyslipidemia, hyperuricemia, obesity, and hyper-homocystenemia have an increased likelihood of developing a stroke.

Keywords: Coronary Heart Disease, Dyslipidemia, Stroke, Type 2 Diabetes.

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Introduction

Stroke is a widespread health crisis that causes long-term disability and death. It is believed that the term "stroke" was introduced into the field of medicine by William Cole in 1689 in his work titled A Physico-Medical Essay Concerning the Late Frequencies of Apoplexies. A transient ischemic attack is characterized by a temporary episode of neurological dysfunction resulting from reduced blood flow to the brain, spinal cord, or retina, without causing immediate tissue damage. [1,2]

Stroke is a complex condition with multiple contributing factors. There are several factors that have been linked to an increased risk of stroke. These include age, sex, family history, high blood pressure, diabetes, high cholesterol, poor diet, obesity, smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, and lack of physical activity. Nevertheless, the impact of

each risk factor on the occurrence of stroke differs across different studies. [3] There are several established risk factors for stroke that should be considered when identifying modifiable risk factors for effective prevention strategies. Prevention is achievable through early detection and by addressing the risk factors that can be modified to reduce the likelihood of stroke. Comorbidities play a crucial role in determining the treatment approach for acute stroke. [4]

Stroke is a significant reason for hospitalization due to neurological conditions in advanced medical facilities. Strokes tend to occur more frequently in older individuals and those who have certain risk factors. These risk factors include hypertension, type 2 diabetes, previous strokes, being male, being post-menopausal as a female, dyslipidemia, and

hyper-homocystenemia. [5,6] This study evaluated the clinical profile of patients who presented with Stroke etiology. Our objective was to examine the correlation between demographic characteristics, various comorbidities, and risk factors in patients who presented with stroke etiology.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in a retrospective manner. A total of 175 patients who were admitted to the medical ward were included in this study. We included all patients with neurological manifestations of stroke in our study. A cross-sectional study was conducted over a period of 1 year, focusing on stroke patients who were hospitalized in the medical ward of a medical college and hospital.

Consent was obtained from all the patients included in this study. Thoroughly collected medical history from all patients and conducted comprehensive examinations of all systems, with special attention to the neurological system. The patient's profile prompted the necessary investigations, including CBC, blood sugar, urea, creatinine, Na⁺, K⁺, lipid profile, CT scan, MRI, and more.

Inclusion Criteria

- Experiencing a first occurrence of cerebral, cerebellar, or brainstem infarction, or a first occurrence of intracerebral, intraventricular, or brainstem hemorrhage.
- Patient or guardian who is willing to provide valid consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- History of stroke.
- Clear indication of a potential embolism.
- A transient ischemic attack.
- Subarachnoid hemorrhage
- Traumatic intracerebral hemorrhage
- History of using antiplatelet or anticoagulant drugs like oral contraceptive pills
- There are certain diseases that can affect the platelet count and packed cell volume/red cell mass. Examples include leukemia, aplastic anemia, ITP, and polycythemia.

Statistical analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 15 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were described as means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range based on their distribution. Qualitative variables were presented as count and percentages. For all tests, confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively.

Results

Out of the 175 stroke patients, there were 20 patients who fell into the young age group (≤ 40 years), while the remaining 155 patients were classified as elderly (>40 years). There were 115 males and 60 females. The average age for infarction in the study population is 56.12 years, with a standard deviation of 19.12. On the other hand, the average age for hemorrhagic stroke was 51.09, with a standard deviation of 21.15. There is a statistically significant age difference ($p=0.000$) between the two types of stroke, with hemorrhagic stroke occurring at a younger age than infarction. The age group with the highest prevalence was 51 – 60 years. A majority of the patients (60%) came from urban areas.

From the entire sample of 175 patients, it was observed that 11.42% ($n=20$) were under the age of 40, and interestingly, all of these individuals were diagnosed with thrombotic stroke. The most common age group was 31-40 years, with 88.57% ($n=155$) of the patients being older than 40 years old. These patients were experiencing both thrombotic and haemorrhagic types of stroke. The age group of 51-60 years was the most prevalent age group. The age group of 51 to 60 years old was found to be the most prevalent for hemorrhagic stroke.

The youngest patient diagnosed with VST was only 18 years old. Out of the 175 patients, a majority of 71.42% did not have any comorbidities. On the other hand, 28.57% of patients had known comorbidities like diabetes mellitus, coronary heart disease, and other conditions. Type 2 diabetes had the highest prevalence among co-morbidities, affecting 19.42% of individuals, while high blood pressure followed closely behind at 5.71%.

There were thirty-three patients with type 2 diabetes who had infarcts, and unfortunately, one patient was also experiencing a hemorrhagic stroke. There are 34 patients who are affected by Type 2 diabetes. Eight out of the ten patients diagnosed with coronary heart disease suffered from an infarct, while two of them had a hemorrhagic stroke.

Of the total 175 patients, a mere 1.14 percent were found to be free from any risk factors associated with stroke. In stark contrast, a staggering 98.85 percent of patients were identified to have risk factors for stroke. Hypertension was found to be the most common risk factor, affecting 82.85 percent of individuals. Male gender and addiction were both identified as risk factors for 65.71 percent of the population. Other risk factors included dyslipidemia (42.85 percent), post-menopausal female (30.85 percent), elevated uric acid (28.57 percent), obesity (25.71 percent), and hyperhomocysteinemia (22.85 percent). Overall, 11.42 percent of patients had a recurring stroke.

Eight female patients had a history of taking OC pills. Out of these patients, six were diagnosed with VST, and two of the female patients were diagnosed with infarct. Out of the 175 patients, a significant majority, 65.71 percent, were found to be struggling with addiction. This addiction could manifest in various forms, such as alcohol, tobacco, or a combination of both. Tobacco addiction had the highest prevalence rate at 17.14 percent, closely followed by alcohol at 16.57 percent.

Individuals who had experienced a thrombotic stroke had a higher likelihood of tobacco addiction, while those who had experienced a hemorrhagic stroke had a higher likelihood of alcohol addiction. In this study, there were a total of 15 male patients who were under the age of 40 years old. All of these patients had risk factors, and four of them had associated comorbidities. In addition, it is worth noting that all of these patients experienced infarcts. Out of the fifteen male patients, eleven were free from any comorbidities. Additionally, nine of them had experienced an ischemic stroke, while two had VST (venous sinus thrombosis). Out of the five patients, four of them had risk factors.

A female patient with comorbidity experienced an ischemic stroke, despite the absence of any known risk factors contributing to her condition. Two out of the six patients diagnosed with VST were male

and had hyperhomocystenemia as a risk factor. All four patients were female and had a history of taking oral contraceptives.

In this specific study, there were a total of one hundred male patients who were over the age of forty and had risk factors. Out of these patients, twenty-five had additional health conditions. There were 22 cases with infarct and three cases with hemorrhage. Out of the total, 56 individuals experienced an infarct, 18 individuals had a hemorrhage, and one individual had a VST. Out of the total, 75 individuals did not have any underlying health conditions.

Out of the 55 female patients over the age of 40, a significant number of them, specifically 54, exhibited risk factors commonly linked to cancer. All 19 patients had underlying health conditions, and each one experienced an infarct. Among the group of 35 females, none had any underlying health conditions. However, 12 of them experienced an infarct, 20 had a haemorrhage, and three had VST. Even though the woman did not have any risk factors, she still experienced a hemorrhagic stroke due to her associated comorbidities. One of the four patients diagnosed with VST was a male with hyperhomocystenemia as a risk factor, while the other three patients were females who had previously used oral contraceptives.

Table 1: Age and Gender distribution

Age	Age group	Total(n=175)	Percentage% (n=175)	Male(n=115)	Female(n=60)
<40* Years (young) (n=20)	18-20	1	0.57%	1	-
	21-30	6	3.42%	4	2
	31-40	13	7.42%	10	3
>40 Years (elder) (n=155)	41-50	29	16.57%	22	7
	51-60	55	31.42%	38	17
	61-70	41	23.42%	24	17
	71-80	27	15.42%	15	12
	81-85	3	1.71%	1	2

*American psychiatric association

Table 2: Type of stroke

Type of Stroke	Total (n=175)	Percentage (n=175)
Thrombotic (n=133)	Infarct	123
	Venous sinus thrombosis (VST)	10
Hemorrhagic (n=42)	42	24%

Table 3: Different Comorbidities and its association with type of stroke

Co-morbidities	Distribution of co-morbidities	Number	Percentage (%) (n=175)	Type of stroke		
				Infarct (n=123)	VST (n=10)	Hemorrhagic (n=42)
Absent(n=125)	Absent	125	71.42%	78	10	37
Present (n=50)	T2 DM	34	19.42%	33	-	1
	IHD	10	5.71%	8	-	2
	OTHER*	6	3.42%	4	-	2

*RHD, Moya-moya disease, TBME, GTCS

Discussion

The key discovery of the present study was the identification of both modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors that play a significant role in the development of ischemic stroke within our population. Some of the risk factors that cannot be changed include being 65 years or older, having a family history of stroke, having a history of TIA, and having had a previous stroke. The modifiable risk factors included hypertension, AF, CAD, valvular heart disease, dyslipidemia, diabetes mellitus, overweight, obesity class one, sedentary lifestyle with low physical activity, and smoking. [6,7]

Age and sex are factors that can contribute to a higher risk of stroke. Stroke becomes more common as people get older, reaching its peak in India during the seventh decade of life. In addition, it is worth noting that the average age for stroke in males was lower than that in females. Approximately 408 patients, or 41.8%, were aged 65 years and older in our study. In 2009, a study discovered a notable difference in stroke incidence between males and females, with males experiencing a roughly 30% higher rate. Additionally, a separate study revealed a notable disparity in the occurrence of stroke between males aged ≥ 40 years and females. [8,9]

There is a significant disparity between the global and regional stroke burden for individuals in the younger age groups (1-29), indicating that there are certain factors contributing to the higher stroke rates among younger adults. Previous research has indicated that low physical activity and hypertension are significant risk factors in young adults. As a result, it may be necessary to develop new criteria for evaluating these risk factors in younger patients. With the population aging, the prevalence of comorbidities and stroke risk factors like hypertension, hyperlipidemia, diabetes, and cardiac diseases is on the rise. As a result, the burden of stroke is expected to be higher in the elderly, as highlighted in our report.

Conclusion

Thrombotic stroke, which includes ischemic stroke and venous sinus thrombosis, is more common than hemorrhagic stroke. Stroke commonly co-occurs with type 2 diabetes mellitus and coronary heart disease (CHD), increasing the risk of developing infarcts. Patients with risk factors such as hypertension, male gender, post-menopausal female, addiction, dyslipidemia, hyperuricemia, obesity, and hyper-homocystenemia have an increased likeli-

hood of developing a stroke. Tobacco addiction ranked highest among all forms of addiction, closely followed by alcohol consumption. It was observed that patients with tobacco addiction had a higher likelihood of developing infarcts. Identifying risk factors early on and promptly addressing modifiable risk factors are key in preventing strokes. This study is on a smaller scale. In order to establish further connections, more extensive studies are necessary.

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